

Women in Sydney's Creative Industries

Report by coursework students of UTS 94663 Navigating
Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, 2022 cohort

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Foreword

This report is part of a series of student-generated series about entrepreneurial ecosystems. Each report is a derivative of their coursework. The subject, 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, is a core subject in the Diploma in Innovation at TD School and a popular elective across other UTS degree programs. The subject was piloted as part of the launch for the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship in 2017¹ and draws on prior research and engagement projects to visualise entrepreneurial ecosystems.²

The subject runs for three weeks in July, during which teams of students are tasked with defining and exploring an entrepreneurial ecosystem, understanding its history and visualising its current state. Based on that knowledge, they then develop proposals to advance the ecosystem.

The reports reflect the work that was presented publicly to invited guests and stakeholders in the subject, as well as members of the public who joined the presentations via the publicly available event page.

General Methodology

In partnership with Investment NSW (e.g., Sydney Startup Hub) and Spark Festival, the cohort of ~45 students was given the option to focus on Sydney CBD, Western Sydney, or Nationally. Additionally, one team was based overseas and was free to choose an international city to navigate.

The general method of this study follows our own method of evaluating ecosystems that has evolved over years of experience, in consultation with an Australian wide network of ecosystem researchers. While our process is not yet well documented, it is entirely consistent with the 2018 guide produced by the German Society for International Collaboration,³ promoted by the Aspen Network of Development Entrepreneurs (ANDE).

In addition to learning about ecosystems, teams engaged with ecosystems in authentic and immersive learning experiences. Stakeholder types and specific stakeholders in the ecosystem were identified based on Stam's seminal (2015) review of ecosystem factors. Insights about the ecosystem were generated by analysing desktop reports and media interviews involved those stakeholders. Where possible, teams conducted their own interviews of key stakeholders, including asking them about the ecosystem's history, evolution and critical events, and their vision for how it may evolve further. By synthesising such reports and interviews from multiple stakeholders, teams developed a composite story of the ecosystem's evolution, visualised its current state and identified specific opportunities for change. These reports present this analysis of the ecosystems' evolution as well as the team's proposal for specific interventions by which to intentionally advance the ecosystem in a specific direction.

The method can be tailored to specific ecosystems, ranging from rural communities through to internationally acclaimed innovation precincts. The breadth of Stam's framework and this method enables pushing back against the myth that innovation and entrepreneurship is primarily the domain of high-tech startups and VCs. While they do play a very important role, they are not the only organisations that matter to create economic growth (Brown & Mason, 2017; Spigel et al., 2020).

Field research for coursework follows the same principles as field research for academic purposes. As a result, the students' work mirrored the process of ecosystem research conducted by Martin Bliemel, for which he has ethics approval (HREC# ETH18-3020).

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¹ Bliemel, M., Schweitzer, J., Roy, G., Keitel, A., Nicolas, L., Miles, M., ... & Griffith, S. (2019, November). Herding cats to co-create cross-university courses in record time. *UIIN University-Industry Interaction Conference 2019*. University Industry Innovation Network.

² Bliemel, M. (2019). University-based entrepreneurial ecosystems and their visualisations. *University-Industry Innovation Magazine*.

³ <https://www.goethe.de/resources/files/pdf197/5.-guide-for-mapping-the-entrepreneurial-ecosystem.pdf>

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1 Definition and Evolution of the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem

1.1 Definition of the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem

The proceeding report will develop upon our previous ecosystem directory, where the outlined boundaries of focus will be female founders among the creative industries within Sydney; an entrepreneurial ecosystem that is complex and dynamic. To gather a well-rounded understanding of the ecosystem, it is also necessary to gather the perspectives from relevant stakeholders, which will be detailed in the ecosystem map, which was gathered from research and interviews with female founders.

1.2 Evolution of the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem

The evolution of the entrepreneurial ecosystem will be explored through the separate lens of female founders and creative industries, with both areas focused on Sydney.

Female Founders in Sydney

Past:

The first-ever female entrepreneur Madam C.J. Walker served as an empowering movement for all women, and she was able to overcome adversity within her saturated industry by building networks and supporting the women within her community, which allowed her to gain a better understanding of her market (Grasshopper, n.d.). Much like Madam C.J. Walker, women today are still facing adversity and bias in business environments and face more outstanding challenges accelerating their start-ups compared to their male counterparts; 82% of female founders believe that gender biases negatively impacted their ability to be able to raise venture capital funding, hindering the journey of their start-up (Billson, 2022). Sydney has attempted to build a more robust culture for female entrepreneurs, and despite ranking in the top 10 for their support for female entrepreneurs in 2016, the city's venture capital funding statistics ranked poorly, with a low percentage of start-up deals and an even smaller amount going towards female-founded start-ups (Palmer-Derrien, 2018). Funding is such a crucial component for start-ups, and it acts as a significant barrier to entry for female entrepreneurs, although, in recent years, there has been more support for female entrepreneurs, a Dell research report found that only 2% of global venture funding capital went toward female-founded start-ups (Palmer-Derrien, 2018). Even if female founders can receive initial funding, they are still only 79% more likely to gain additional funding than their male counterparts, who are 83% successful (Fulltoon, 2020). For decades, women in business have had to work together and are encouraged to assist other women on their journey, this has impacted female founders when seeking funding. Some research has suggested that they are more likely to be successful in gaining funding from female venture capitalists, who are twice as likely to obtain funding (Elesser, 2022).

Present

Much of the reason that female entrepreneurs have been able to overcome these adversities in obtaining funding and creating a successful foundation for their business to grow from has emerged as a result of the willingness of successful leaders in the industry to provide support and knowledge to their peers as well as those looking to or just entering into the start-up space. These women have been able to pave successful start-ups, overcoming the bias, barriers of entry, and lack of support faced by women in the start-up industry (Goorah, 2021). They are now actively creating pathways and attempting to remove these obstacles for future generations, this has seen significant growth in the number of female-founded start-ups with a 46% growth rate in the past 20 years (Billson, 2022). Many of the key stakeholders we selected to engage with are currently participating in mentorships or working with universities and start-up hubs supporting young people and those looking to enter a creative industry or their start-up, providing them with valuable information and tools to accelerate their journey as female entrepreneurs. The support these successful female founders are willing to provide is evident by the team's number of responses from the enthusiasm to share their time and knowledge to help us with this assignment.

Future

In recent years the Australian Government's support for female entrepreneurs has increased, with the Australian Government announcing \$52.2 million in grant funding for the 'Boosting Female Founders Initiative', which is currently on its second round (business.gov.au, 2022). This grant aims to stimulate women-led innovative start-ups, assist women in overcoming barriers of entry and enable them to scale up. There was also a 'Women Funding Program' in 2021 that aims to promote financial wellbeing and security, health and engagement, encouraging more diversity in the workplace and increasing innovation (NSW Government, n.d.). Funding has previously been and is still one of the most significant barriers to entry for female entrepreneurs, these funding stimulants from the Government and support from within the EE and the growing start-up community in Australia are currently emerging and will hopefully see the number of successful female entrepreneurs continue to grow (see Appendix A for timeline).

Creative Industries in Australian History

Past

The rich history of the cultural and creative industries within Australia has revolutionised how Australia's economy functions and the value these creative companies add to innovation, making and design. The concept of creative industries was first documented in 1994 in Australia, designed to embody new IT opportunities and the growing movement of global culture made possible through digital media. Prime Minister at this time, Paul Keating, developed the 'Creative Nation' policy to fund an additional \$250 million to cultural institutions and broaden the cultural term into areas such as film, radio, libraries and the arts (Moore, 2014). The industrial revolution was deemed highly influential on society's life, such as new affordability, workforce, and consumption patterns. The creative industries had developed from cultural industries due to the industrial revolution in the 19th century, allowing culture to be reproduced and used for widespread distribution. Through this changing environment, creative industries were viewed in the context of digitalisation, leading to the rise of popular and commercial culture. These fields were becoming more valuable, and new jobs were being generated, creating a solid foundation for competitiveness (Moore, 2014). Traditionally, this field was only primarily viewed as a public good, contributing little to the workforce and economy and requiring government support to survive in Australia (Australian Academy of the Humanities, 2021).

Present

The creative industries within Australia have seen massive growth and hold great value for the Australian economy. The creative ecosystem is highly dynamic, contributing to cultural diversity, social inclusion, environmental sustainability and technological advancement. Creativity and innovation are essential in Australia's recovery and resilience to past and current economic challenges (Australian Trade and Investment Commission, 2022). In 2018-19 Australia's cultural and creative industries generated \$115.8 billion for the economy, increasing over the past ten years (Cunningham, 2022). From 2016 to 2017, the creative sector employed 600,000 people, as The Australian Academy of Humanities reported, making these individuals highly skilled and ultimately allowing their talents to be exported and knowledge shared around the globe. Prior to the Covid-19 pandemic, cultural and creative activity represented 6.4% of GDP and 8.1% of the workforce. The creative economy can contribute to national recovery through high technology and high-value professional services (A New Approach, 2020). This Entrepreneurial ecosystem has allowed Australia's economy to become versatile, resilient and qualified. The evolution of creative skills has allowed individuals and the surrounding environment to be part of fundamental change for the future. Australia's creative economy has flourished due to the power of pioneering females in the workforce, which is the key to self-expression and innovation.

Future

The creative industries were included as a Strategy for 21st Century Australia by the Australian Government in 2011, as this industry sector was seen to have great potential to drive Australia's economy and Australian entrepreneurs to build a better future where more individuals could connect and be part of (Grushka, 2018). Creative industries and creative skills are fundamental for the future of Australia's economy as these skills will become mainstream knowledge. The creative industry sector is one of the top 5 innovation-active industries, with 10-28% of employers holding a creative qualification, making these skills vital for future employment growth (Cunningham, 2022). New technologies and innovation in the workforce have had a persuasive effect on the future of work, as employment in the digital intensive industries has doubled over the past 30 years. Creative skills in fields such as digital media, performing, and visual arts are exceedingly resistant and will be in high demand in the future of Australia's economy. Original thoughts and innovation will influence and be critical to positioning Australia to benefit from new technologies and sources of growth (Bureau of Communications Arts and Research, Department of Communications and Arts, 2019). (see Appendix B for timeline).

Figure 1: Ecosystem Map for Women in Sydney's Creative Industries

Figure 2: Legend for the Ecosystem Map

1.3 Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Map Explained

The main and the centre element of this Entrepreneurial Ecosystem map in Figures 1 and 2 is the talent which in this case is female founders in the creative industries based in Sydney. The icons around the female founders, which are marked with white arrows, are the key elements. Seven critical elements connected to the ecosystem are founder, finance, support services, physical infrastructure, education, leadership, media, and networking. Each element has its actors (purple lines), and some interconnections between the elements are marked with bold red dotted lines. Sydney Angels are the best place to start for those business owners looking for angel investors in the Sydney area.

Finance elements in the ecosystem hold significant accounts in the birth of a business. There are several actors to help new businesses to reach their initial costs, such as Government, Self-Funding, Venture capitalists, and Angel Investors. Michelle Deaker is the main stakeholder for the Venture Capitalist in this stakeholder map. Deaker (the founding partner and managing director of OneVenture), along with two other high-profile female venture capitalists, Ingrid Maes (the managing director of Woolworths) and Andrea Gardiner (the chief executive and founder of Jelix Ventures), have organised a program to assist female VCs in Australia with mentoring, education, and networking opportunities (Bennett, 2022). Whereas the Australian Government offers funding for female founders of start-up businesses by providing a program called "Boosting Female Founders Initiative". Moreover, the New South Wales Government (where the boundaries of this EE map are) has their agency focusing on investment and economic development.

The finance element is also linked with the support services elements since programs like investment NSW, boosting female services, and the venture capitalists are considered supports in financial sectors for female founders in starting their businesses. Besides finance, the support services element also connects with physical infrastructure, media, leadership, and networking. The support services element has two actors that play significant roles in the ecosystem since they could assist in the growth of the business. Springboard Enterprise (SBE) Australia, the NSW Startup Community, and Sydney Startup Hub. In Sydney, SBE Australia is a business accelerator for women, providing access to networks, knowledge, and tools. The NSW Startup Community is a community for start-up owners to connect and expand their network with other start-up owners in New South Wales, focusing on those in Sydney Startup Hub.

The physical infrastructure element is also linked with support services, where this element is also connected with support services. This element holds accounts of the birth of a business since it offers space for business owners to expand and work on their ideas. The key stakeholders/actors of these elements are the co-working space. As the highest-density start-up space in the Southern Hemisphere (Investment NSW, 2022), Sydney Startup Hub is home to more than 450 start-ups. Sydney Startup Hub is also joint attributes with the support services and networking element (marked with blue dotted lines). Additionally, since this map focuses on the creative industries, another ecosystem stakeholder is i-Hub, a music start-up incubator from the Australian Institute of Music (AIM, 2020).

The education element connects with the media element in the ecosystem map. Education could be accessed through several media such as the internet. However, education could be divided into two types of actors, formal and informal.

The leadership element also linked with support services element for Government's support agent are services that support female business founders.

The media element is related not only to the education element but also to the support services and the networking element. People could use social media such as LinkedIn to socialise and expand business founders' networks. Other than that, people could also find and connect via the NSW Startup Community.

Networking elements play a significant role in the ecosystem. The ability to network with other start-ups could affect the rise and growth of a start-up since it would expand their connection and assist each other. The actors visualised on the map are Female Founders Startup Program, Spark Festival, and Local Innovation Network. The Female Founders Startup Program is a program by the

NSW Government to educate female founders on their business journey. Other Networking program by the NSW Government is the Local Innovation Network which they are committed to developing and supporting start-ups, where Spark Festival is an event for entrepreneurs, innovators, and start-up founders to connect businesses in Australia.

2 Leverage Proposal

2.1 Vision of the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem

Based on guidance from research and analysis of interviews, our vision for the focused entrepreneurial ecosystem in the next ten years notices a more significant level of growth and prosperity if adequate financial and non-financial support is granted and barriers to entry are reduced. Given the value relevant stakeholders within the ecosystem contribute to the creativity, innovation and productivity of the greater economy through a unique skill set, there is immense potential for female founders among the creative industries to excel and gain greater respect within Sydney's start-up ecosystem. This opportunity is pivotal as a rising social agenda prioritises gender equality and equal opportunity (Strawser et al., 2021). Additionally, the constant technological advancements, such as artificial intelligence and the rise of social media, are increasing accessibility and knowledge for those at all levels of expertise, where entrepreneurs must adapt their skills toward a more digital future (Frankiewicz & Chamorro-Premuzic, 2020). Current efforts of mentors and support networks, e.g. Business Chicks, female funding opportunities, e.g. SheEO, and government funding for female business owners injected into the NSW budget are examples of appropriate, actionable levers towards the right path.

2.2 Limitations and exploring opportunities

To witness the EE flourish and for the current ecosystem to meet the future one harmoniously, barriers need to be addressed and deconstructed by stakeholders in the position to intervene. Ultimately, concerns around power imbalances, expectations and stereotypes must be addressed. Key barriers our group identified, particularly from the interviews conducted, that are currently experienced or propelled on to females founder creatives include:

- Lack of awareness and access to government funding and venture capitalists. Companies founded by women have been historically underfunded compared to their male counterparts.
- Perceived lack of experience and skills for female founders. It can impact confidence and contributes to higher risk awareness. This can lead to not maximising each opportunity presented, for example, when pitching to investors.
- Expectations to be the primary carer in family dynamics - restricts time devoted to developing a start-up, and financial pressure leads to an unstable work/life balance.
- Lack of access to relatable role models and sponsors who have been on the journey

Thus, taking an optimistic outlook, there is immense opportunity for growth within the ecosystem to support and nurture female founders to reach the maximum potential of creativity, innovation and productivity. From a richer understanding of the entrepreneurial ecosystem through research and interviews, key stakeholders identified that are in a position to intervene and accelerate are the government, venture capitalists, universities, venues, networking organisers, accelerators, incubators, and Sydney Start-up Hub and other hubs and co-working spaces.

The ecosystem presents deeply-rooted social concerns regarding the belief of women and power within the entrepreneurial landscape. However, to challenge and minimise the limitations uncovered, we propose the following levers to accelerate the current ecosystem by solely focusing on a females experience, where we will take a female orientated approach.

2.3 Lever One

When divulging the complexities related to the constraints on development for female founders in creative industries within 8kms of the Sydney CBD. Stakeholder interviews and further research of the scope revealed the issue of the false self and cultural perceptions of female entrepreneurs to lack sufficient entrepreneurial skills for business success. These factors hinder the ability of females within the creative industry to finance their business ventures, thus constricting the growth and development of the ecosystem.

The Global OECD average reflects this. Between 2014 and 2018, females were 35% less likely to personally believe they have adequate entrepreneurial skills for business (OECD, 2022). Although it is essential to note this figure could potentially be reflective of a skills gap that has multiple quantifiable

explanations, through the stakeholder interview process, we have identified the causation of this statistic concerning female founders within creative industries to be related to self-perception and presentation which is shaped by the culture of the investment landscape. Further research affirms this idea, highlighted by key stakeholders such as Sarah Neill, as culture provides individuals with a “prototype” for the construction of self-identity, self-perception and self-presentation (Usborne & Taylor, 2010) all factors which have effect start-up financing.

To aid in the resolution of this long-standing issue, we propose a mentorship-style program. Our further research has revealed a “transformational leadership style” in this proposition, that being mentorship is effective for female entrepreneurs concerning personal and professional development (Laukhuf & Malone, 2015). This program based in Sydney CBD would be designed to aid stakeholders in successfully securing finance or generating additional capital from investors. After connecting with stakeholders such as Ms Neill, who recognises the increase in programs such as ‘F to F’, which Neill founded, and others that are increasing in popularity, it is evident through the wide gender funding gap that these programs hit a roadblock at some point. Where female entrepreneurs have established themselves beyond the idea generation stage, the reality of the need to finance these ideas becomes a significant barrier to the EE, with males receiving 50 times more VC than females (Balachandra, 2020).

In this proposed program, female entrepreneurs would be mentored by female venture capitalists (VC) such as Lauren Capelin, Georgie Turner, Hannah Yan Field and Emily Close, all female Sydney-based VCs who have in the past been open about the VC landscape in Sydney by participating in things such as the UTS Women in Venture blog series.

Female entrepreneurs would have the opportunity to pitch themselves and their idea in a risk-free, supportive environment. Feedback from the VC mentors will give entrepreneurs the knowledge of the VC environment and establish and develop skills relating to self-presentation directly translated into learning the most efficient and effective ways to attract finance. Initially, the program would have availability of 5 entrepreneurs for every 1 VC. The program would run over a 2-month period where VCs and entrepreneurs would connect in groups on an online video call and share ideas and progress fortnightly over the 2 months. VC mentors would be supported by their VC firms such as Reinventure, Tidal Ventures, or Gronk Ventures, as these VC firms gain from this program by having exclusive access to entrepreneurs and exposure to the new ideas entering the market, establishing a mutually beneficial relationship between mentors and mentees.

2.4 Lever Two

In the process of EE establishment and advancement, values, social structure and gender socialisation place the burden of disadvantage primary on female stakeholders (Fay & Williams, 1993). The stakeholder interview of Paula Jones, founder and CEO of Blind Chihuahua, highlighted the barrier and evident presence of “bro culture” within the EE of the creative industry of Sydney CBD and the surrounding area (see Appendix C). Although further academic sources mainly analyse US EE, personalised stakeholder research affirms this idea. Once we examined the multilayered cause of the barrier, we could conclude the reasoning behind this issue and thus produce a practical lever.

As outlined in this report above, the advancement of female entrepreneurs within the EE has come a long way from its origins however, there is still much room for improvement. As a result of this lingering “bro culture” for many enterprises and individuals, the open immersion of females into the EE is still perceived as uncertainty as it is directly impacted by not only collective interest but also external factors to the EE (Achrol & Stern, 1988). The reality of Sydney's business culture is that it is highly male-dominated, which mirrors the majority of stakeholders in the finance sector. Stakeholders within the EE, such as Sarah Neill, revealed this barrier stating “these investors (that majority being males) will not invest in things they do not understand”, an issue very common for female entrepreneurs within the creative industry as many ventures fall into this “category” (see Appendix D). This mindset, coupled with the attitude of investors towards female entrepreneurs uncovered by Dana Kanze, where investors ask males 67% opportunity/growth questions and female entrepreneurs get asked 66% downside risk questions (Kanze, 2022), has constructed this significant barrier.

We propose the starting point to break down this barrier is through the activator of education. As gender equality in education is a significant contributor to gender equality on the broader EE (Chen, 2004), providing education on gender equity in the Sydney business space will catalyse this movement. This education course would be presented as a series of short modules that business students must complete as core course material. This would be implemented by tertiary institutions such as UTS, UNSW and USYD. All of these institutions already require students to take part in other compulsory modules in other areas, such as correct academic conduct modules and student code of conduct therefore gender equity in the business module would be logistically not challenging to implement. The aim of these modules would be to educate through increasing awareness of gender inequality between stakeholders in the EE additionally, implementing this as part of the core modules, allows students to recognise its importance.

The creation of these modules can be outsourced to companies such as 'Entrepreneurs Organisation'. It can be managed by members of faculty such as UTS Dr Bilquis Ghani, the gender equity programs manager.

2.5 Conclusion

Overall, the expected value of our leverage proposal is to challenge and disrupt the existing entrepreneurial ecosystem and the accompanying beliefs and frameworks within Sydney's entrepreneurial landscape that hinder a female founder's opportunities and triumph. Particularly regarding the social and cultural concerns around gender quality and equal opportunity. Thereby, the levers aim to target both the entrepreneurial ecosystem at large and the activators by recognising the value female founders bring to Sydney's overall creativity, innovation and productivity as they provide a new perspective and unique skill set. Where mentoring, networking and educating those within the ecosystem offer a two-fold benefit for all stakeholders.

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3 Appendices

Appendix A: Female Founders Timeline

Appendix B: Creative Industries Timeline

Appendix C: Excerpt from interview with Paula Jones, founder and CEO of Blind Chihuahua

“I think the bro culture is still very much alive and well. I don’t think it’s conscious or intentional, but in the creative tech industry there still isn’t enough young women getting deep into the tech side.

We’re exploring new creative paradigms with Metaverse type experiences and building blockchain games, and we find that culture is still very heavily driven by teams with little to no women either on the tech teams or upper management teams. I think we really need to encourage more women into the creative tech arts from school onwards. We have the opportunity to build an entirely new ecosystem for humans to gather in and I find there’s not enough gender diverse voices driving that from the top. There are some outstanding women in the field but I feel like they have to shout louder and spend more time promoting themselves in order to be heard.” - Paula Jones

Appendix D: Excerpt from interview with Sarah Neill, founder and CEO of Mys Tyler

“Yeah, bias that exists where whereby both men and women investors ask different questions of women than they do of men. And as a result they get different information and as a result it leads to less funding and less investment. So I think that sort of is happening globally. I’m not sure whether any of that is different to what’s happening in the Sydney environment.” - Sarah Neill

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